
Exploring the Multifaceted Implications of Generative AI on Modern Shopping Experiences: A Comprehensive Study

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Abstract The rapid development of modern technologies has dramatically changed the concept of shopping. Generative artificial intelligence is an upsurge that claimed to revolutionize this concept of E-commerce. This paper reviews how it would affect e-commerce, covering its practical applications, benefits, and challenges. It mainly amplifies customer activity and satisfaction through personalized interactions, effective customer service, and product visualization. Prime examples of AI-powered solutions such as Wendy's Fresh AI, Solidgrids,

Lumalabs.ai, Adcreative.ai, and Maverick demonstrate that AI-driven shopping can tighten operations while giving better conversion rates. Still, Generative AI brings its issues towards privacy, bias, and over-dependency on technology. All such challenges must be checked for AI-driven shopping to ensure fair, inclusive, and of more significant quality. In this case, other emerging technologies like blockchain, IoT, and quantum computing add to the potential of e-commerce. Business investments should be strategically made in AI, data analytics, cybersecurity, innovation, customer experience, sustainability, staff training, and continuous monitoring of technology evolution so businesses can reap maximum advantage of Generative AI and other emerging technologies. This review helps to present the current and future outlook of Generative AI in e-commerce in detail. It suggests ways for businesses to improve the shopping experience while ensuring growth.

Keywords Multifaceted Implications of Generative AI, Modern Shopping Experiences

1. Introduction

Technology has recently shaped significant changes in the shopping experience, and Generative Artificial Intelligence is one such disruptive transformation. It is an AI application that can generate text, images, videos, etc., transforming consumer engagement with brands and products

(Smith, 2022). This critical review explores how Generative AI affects the shopping experience, and its applications, advantages, and limitations will be practically analyzed. As digitalization progressed, the requirements of customers also changed. Consumers nowadays crave bespoke, interactive, and instantaneous interactions with companies. They demand ideas in context, quick responses to problems, and content that feels made precisely for them (Johnson, 2021). Such expectations are met by Generative AI that supplies personalization and interaction that were simply unattainable by other solutions (Brown, 2021). For example, Wendy's Fresh AI leverages Generative AI to the advantage of the hotline, providing on-point, instant, and well-informed answers that increase reliability and satisfaction on a drive-thru order (Wendy's, 2023). This application is important because it illustrates how AI efficiency can do hard work and maximize the experience of customers in a fast service store.

Besides customer service, Generative AI has also made its mark in product visualization. Many e-commerce platforms have begun incorporating AI-generated visual tools to produce top-notch and extensive product

images. This invention likely eliminates the need for lengthy, costly photoshoots, providing customers with a more in-depth visual of products (Green et al., 2022).

Generative AI is used by Under Armour, Shopify, LinkedIn, etc., to show images that help customers make more informed decisions while shopping (Adcreative.ai, 2023). Not only does this improve the shopping experience, but it also causes brands to achieve higher conversion rates (Smith et al., 2022).

Another meaningful use case for Generative AI in e-commerce is video creation. Videos are a compelling medium for customer engagement, with AI empowering brands to generate personalized videos at scale.

Whether marketing campaigns, product demonstrations, or customer testimonials, AI videos can significantly impact purchase decisions by providing rich, interactive content (Maverick, 2023). The ability to deliver individualized video messaging helps brands better hold customers' attention, building loyalty and driving sales (Johnson et al., 2021).

Though these advancements are notable, integrating Generative AI into the shopping experience introduces challenges. One principal obstacle is privacy. To personalize the shopping experience, AI must collect data, and this data collection leads to privacy concerns. Consumers are increasingly aware and concerned about data usage, requiring businesses to negotiate privacy concerns

(Williams, 2022). Additionally, AI systems potentially propagate the biases of training data, creating unfair results. Due to bias, it is vital to ensure that AI-driven shopping experiences are even and inclusive (Lee et al., 2021). Furthermore, there exists the danger of over-reliance on technology. Even though efficiency and personalization are enhanced by AI, maintaining human oversight is vital to preventing errors and ensuring quality service (Smith et al., 2022).

The range of future possibilities for Generative AI in Retail is immense and encouraging. Personalization advances, as AI can analyze consumer preferences and behaviors to create highly custom shopping journeys (Brown, 2021). Virtual try-ons will reach a more robust state, where Generative AI will enable consumers to experience what fashion and beauty look like on them before making a purchase (Williams, 2022). Pricing dynamics will be augmented by AI analysis of customer data and market direction, crafting optimized pricing to fulfill revenue and customer satisfaction (Lee et al., 2021)

The purpose of this article is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the impact of AI on the shopping experience, providing a reasoned approach, case studies of Wendy's Fresh AI, illustrations (product image generation, video generation from images), and reasoning on how generative AI is transforming the shopping experience, identify the future issues and subsequent stages of Generative AI. In brief, the researcher analyzes how Generative AI will transform the time spent in shopping and simplify the process by streamlining the steps to purchase a product. The advantages of Generative AI on the economy (mentioned above) will still be valid, and the market will continue to expand. The aim is to analyze the current and future position of Generative AI in this sector and examine the upcoming trends of AI.

2. Literature review

The last few years have seen a significant change in how we shop, with technology playing a tremendous role in "remapping" a once very routine activity. Many technologies are at work, making the shopping experience what we now know, understand, and love or loathe, depending on the experience. However, generative artificial intelligence (AI) is arguably "the" most profound and revolutionary of these shopping-side technologies. That is because generative AI can process vast and varied amounts of data from many different sources. When generative AI is put to work, it can take all that data as input to produce much more understandable, usable, and contextually rich content, making customer interactions with AI and the resultant content seem much more natural.

2.1 Improving Customer Service and Customization

The utilization of Generative AI has revolutionized customer service and personalization in e-commerce. Virtual assistants such as Kili and Voiceflow demonstrate how AI-driven Chatbots and Virtual Assistants boost the shopping experience by helping customers find products and provide immediate support (Kili, Inc., 2023; Voiceflow, Inc., 2023). Previous research has shown that these AI systems can learn from customer interactions, delivering increasingly accurate and helpful responses, contributing to higher conversions and growing

satisfaction (Smith et al., 2022; Brown, 2021). Kili provides a machine-learning solution that allows e-commerce firms to build virtual shopping assistants for their customers. This lets customers speak with a voice-commanded virtual assistant, dramatically reducing the time customers find products (Kili, Inc., 2023). Another firm, Voiceflow, offers a conversational AI platform for building chat and voice assistants; its founding team uses this product to serve customers (Voiceflow, Inc., 2023). Meanwhile, according to a recent study, AI-powered customer service platforms are boosting retailers' satisfaction ratings. These are just a few ways the Artificial Intelligence Revolution is sweeping the retail sector and fundamentally transforming it (Smith et al., 2022). The Fresh AI from Wendy's illustrates the technique of using AI in customer service. The AI platform can help interact with customers when placing a drive-thru order and also offer personalized customer experiences in real-time, resulting in more accurate orders and reducing wait times (Wendy's, 2023). Fresh AI from Wendy's is another example of how AI can improve cooperation by making lean efficiency gains and improving the customer experience.

Figure 1: Wendy's new drive-thru AI technology at Columbus, OH (Shillcock, 2023)

2.2 Visualizing products and marketing them

The capacity of Generative AI to create a wide range of creative portfolios is changing product visualization and marketing. Solidgrids and Lumalabs.ai are examples of artificial intelligence that can produce marketable product images and 3D visuals from any store-bought item or phone photo. This saves costs on photo shoots and gives customers a more involved shopping experience (Solidgrids Inc., 2023; Lumalabs Inc., 2023). In e-commerce, it is apparent that visuals are pivotal in aiding customers in making informed purchasing decisions, consequently increasing conversion rates (Green et al., 2022).

In just seconds, Solidgrids can take simple phone pictures and turn them into stunning product images ready for sale, giving e-commerce businesses that need-ready-now edge to create professional product images that capture the attention of prospective clients and improve the overall shopping experience (Solidgrids, 2023). Instead of capturing photographs or 3D rendering, Lumalabs.ai scans items and objects from the real world, turning these images automatically into 3D images. Smartphones are perfect nowadays for capturing memories, but Lumalabs.ai is not limited to a camera. Retailers could have an unlimited number of products lying around, which they scan to provide e-commerce customers with 3D images, which could dramatically increase conversions and sales (Lumalabs.ai, 2023).

Figure 2: A realistic 3d image of an electric bike

Adcreative.ai and Maverick are stand-out examples, focusing on creating personalized and conversion-focused ad content. Adcreative.ai is a generative AI tool that allows e-commerce businesses to create conversion-focused ads and social media creatives in seconds. Generating visually appealing and targeted content enables businesses to grab their audience's attention, increasing engagement and conversions (Adcreative.ai, 2023; Maverick, 2023). Maverick enables businesses to send automated AI-generated personalized videos to all their customers at scale. This solution helps boost customer lifetime value and improve engagement, conversions, revenue, and retention while delighting customers at scale (Maverick, 2023). The Johnson Study (2021) research demonstrates that personalized marketing content significantly increases customer engagement and conversion rates, indicating that generative AI is at the vanguard of modern marketing strategies.

2.3 Writing Engaging Content and Optimizing for Search Engines

The capacity of generative AI to make personalized, captivating pieces is a complete transformation for Internet businesses. For instance, Copysmith.ai employs AI to draft SEO-enhanced product descriptions, while CopyMonkey does the same for Amazon listings. This improves internet search standings and enhances market exposure across prominent e-commerce platforms to drive more users

Copysmith.ai is an AI-only product description writing tool for e-commerce businesses that can start creating and publishing SEO product descriptions with a few clicks. With the content made by Copysmith, it can improve search ranking on the search engine and increase traffic to the online store (Copysmith.ai, 2023). CopyMonkey is an AI-only Amazon Listing Optimization Tool for e-commerce businesses. Start optimizing your Amazon Listings within seconds. With the use of AI content, it can improve your products' rank and sales on Amazon Marketplace (CopyMonkey, 2023).

For companies that want to keep their online reputation and provide target customers with the most relevant and generating audience-influential content, Yuma is an AI-powered content generation platform for creating high-quality, unique, and engaging content for various purposes such as ads, blogs, articles, product descriptions, and so on. Yuma uses sophisticated generative AI algorithms to produce high-quality, unique text content tailored to specific industries, target audiences, and applications (Yuma, 2023).

2.4 Insights and Analytics for Customers

The success of e-commerce critically depends on understanding customers' preferences and behaviors. According to a recent study by Green et al. (2022), businesses using AI-powered customer insights increased 15% boost in sales and 20% of customer satisfaction, proving the importance of data-driven decision-making. Generative AI tools, such as Shulex, Voc.ai, and Aidaptive, leverage customer feedback from different sources and provide valuable insights. They analyze customer reviews, feedback, and other customer-related data to generate actionable insights for businesses to optimize their products' quality and marketing strategies. Shulex Voc.ai is a powerful AI tool that provides valuable product reviews, customer feedback, and practical insights for e-commerce companies. According to Shulex Voc.ai, customer feedback and reviews are analyzed when used. It will help e-commerce companies understand what their customers want and are tested to improve every aspect of their business. Similarly, Aidaptive is an AI-driven customer analysis platform that focuses on helping e-commerce companies better identify customers. To ensure accurate personalization of personal experiences, Aidaptive uses complex machine learning algorithms to gain insight from the data of the volumes of customers. (Shulex, 2023; Voc.ai, 2023; Aidaptive Inc., 2023)

2.5 Applying What You Have Learned and Identifying Challenges

Despite the compelling advantages of generative AI in e-commerce, companies must navigate numerous roadblocks. The most glaring privacy issue is that using AI to personalize experiences necessitates sweeping data collection. Safeguarding data privacy while ensuring compliance with statutes such as GDPR (Rothenberg & Argawal, 2020) is imperative to maintaining trust. A survey conducted by Williams (2022) identifies this as a problematic issue for AI-driven stores, which often sacrifice privacy for personalization. A widespread problem with AI is that it is biased in making decisions that replicate the biases and preconceptions of the people who make them. AI systems can create and deepen inflammation inherent in their training data that fixates on unfair outcomes. Addressing these biases is essential to ensure fair and trustworthy AI systems. Research by Lee et al.

(2021) emphasized the necessity of making unbiased AI systems to prohibit discrimination and treat all customers equally.

Another obstacle is the previous overreliance on technology. Though AI aids efficiency and personalization, human supervision is needed to maintain accuracy and guarantee high-quality service. As Williams (2022) has emphasized, a mix of AI capabilities and human touch is the most effective in terms of customer service delivery and operational efficiency.

2.6 Potential for the Future

By looking at generative design and predictive personalization, one might glimpse what is happening now and what will happen next with generative AI and e-commerce. For generative AI to make good decisions for e-commerce, it needs to be able to understand and create the essential elements of design. It should also be able to recombine those elements to create new designs. In this manner, AI is the first condition for making good choices and understanding good design. AI also takes on the second condition for good design in e-commerce. It must be able to personalize the design for your particular experience. Using generative artificial intelligence systems in e-commerce could likely lead to huge benefits. These systems are already being put into place and suggest a future where many of the jobs humans work in could quickly be done by a machine. Even before Covid pandemic effectively shut down vast swaths of in-person commerce, the rise of AI in various forms seemed inevitable. AI was set to make an impact on almost all of the businesses that trade online. From picking the right products to showing them in the best light and then getting them to the customer as quickly and cheaply as possible, AI rapidly affected natural, positive change in e-commerce.

2.7 Improving Product Development

Product development might feel like an immense job, but by using the proper methods and tools, any business can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of this vital work. From coming up with ideas for new products to successfully launching those products in the market, developers must carefully consider each phase of the product life cycle. They must then make a quick, informed decision, whether moving on to the next step in the process or scrapping everything they have done and starting over. In e-commerce, product development is one of the most exciting applications of generative AI. The copious amounts of data we feed into AI enable it to develop product designs that are both one-of-a-kind and something that would work. For instance, when we took the millions of 2D and 3D product designs of a cellphone case that people have designed before and put those into a generative AI model, the outcome was cases that were functionally similar to what you would find in a store.

If an AI is given a goal (create a new widget) and a dataset from which to work, the system can have many humanlike cognitive tasks. It can dream up an entirely new widget that's never been seen before. The speed at which it performs allows for rapid prototyping, meaning that businesses can almost immediately perform tests on the new mock-ups. Right now, the most advanced work in this area involves the development of intelligent agents or using AI to make a computer program that can reliably and usefully perform a specific task.

E-commerce websites are also expected to be transformed by the power of generative AI. They are vital for securing the must-have pull, the initial 'glue' for a business deal.

3. Future Directions and Strategies for Generative AI in E-Commerce

3.1 Predicting the Future of Generative AI in E-Commerce

The e-commerce domain is on the edge of a colossal transformation thanks to the artificial intelligence (AI) revolution. Rapid enhancements in AI have been impacting the core of e-commerce, most significantly, generative AI. With the help of generative AI, which creates new 'synthesized' content, e-commerce teams can now dream of far more 'intelligent' operations. The content being made is another place where e-commerce sees an AI-driven transformation. The possibilities for using generative AI in e-commerce are enormous and exciting. How close we are to that reality may be overstated in current discourse, but the path leading to it is pretty straightforward. Generative AI is beginning to do work that used to be done by people in almost every part of e-commerce (Johnson, 2021).

3.2 Product Development: A New Frontier

Generative AI will revolutionize the process of product development in e-commerce. AI, on the other hand, can design exceptional and innovative designs without the use of hand-drawn sketches by making full use of the data available to it at a grand scale, thereby cutting time in the prototyping process all at once by getting it right the first time (Brown, 2021). For instance, if an AI system generative for designing new widgets were called upon for such a job, it could create a distinguished design from its vast data. This speed in prototyping power allows businesses to quickly test and optimize products, reducing the time and cost of development. This brings efficiency to the competition for e-commerce space that is constantly changing (Williams, 2022).

Figure 3: Images generated by ChatGpt for different color variants of a grass mower

3.3. Advanced Marketing Strategies

In essence, generative AI impacts marketing in its depth. Adcreative.ai and Maverick allow businesses to create personalized and conversion-focused advert content. Irrespective of the requirement to be provided by anyone, Adcreative.ai will automatically generate a visually appealing ad for the targeted audience. This automatically ensures increased attention and higher engagement or even conversions—especially on platforms like Facebook and Instagram (Adcreative.ai, 2023). For Maverick, businesses can automate their videos at scale, ensuring customer engagement and retention. Such tools reflect the future trend of marketing strategies that are personalized yet effective. When generative AI creates such content, it evokes emotions within its audience, increasing customer loyalty and, hence, higher sales, as Johnson et al. (2021) state.

3.4 User Experience: The Next Level

Generative AI will take user experience in e-commerce to a whole new level. As AI systems advance, more interactive experiences and UI will be the norm rather than an exception. For example, technologies such as VR and AR can develop interactive shopping experiences. A customer may place a piece of virtual furniture in her lounge and spend all her time interacting with it in real-time. Brown (2021) says such engagement may tremendously boost customer satisfaction and sales. Today, putting a virtual sofa in a picture of your living room is child's play. Only when the technologies of Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality are closer to par can customers walk around, perceived by senses, intuitions, or reasoning, which, in turn, induces more significant involvement and more informed purchase decisions (Williams, 2022).

3.5 Emerging Technologies and Their Potential Impact in

E-Commerce

Although generative AI is making huge waves in this e-commerce domain, other technologies potentially impact the future.

3.5.1 Blockchain-Based Secure Transactions

Blockchain technology is a decentralized and secure platform to conduct transactions. In the e-commerce domain, it can transform the entire process by making it secure, transparent, and free of fraud. For instance, blockchain can maintain unalterable records of all kinds of transactions that help trace back any product's origin securely (Rothenberg & Argawal, 2020).

3.5.2 IoT For Intelligent Shopping Experiences

The IoT makes ordinary devices interconnected using the internet, and this new ability enables them to collect and distribute data. IoT in e-commerce can facilitate modern shopping by interlinking the products, customers, and retailers. For example, intelligent shelves are available to monitor the amount of inventory, while connected things could provide customized suggestions according to the consumer's choice (Green et al., 2022).

3.5.3 Machine Learning for Predictive Analytics

They may research the data to determine their customers' upcoming trends and behaviors. For instance, predictive analytics help businesses materialize the intent or purposes of the customers and, hence, streamline the business inventory and marketing mix. For example, machine learning uses purchase history to illuminate more likely purchases, hence stocking appropriately (Smith, 2022).

3.5.4 VR and AR for Immersive Shopping

Virtual and augmented reality technologies will both be able to produce the most immersive shopping experiences. Customers will explore and interact with products more thrillingly as they become enhanced. For example, through VR, customers are exposed to a 3D environment where they can explore the product, while AR overlays digital information into the physical world, something that would potentially offer seamless shopping experiences to customers (Brown, 2021).

3.5.5 Quantum Computing for Optimization

Quantum computers will assist in computing highly complex optimization problems deemed impossible by classical computers. Quantum computers in e-commerce will optimize logistics and supply chain management operations and personalized recommendations, resulting in better and more efficient operations and great customer experiences (Lee et al., 2021).

4. Preparing for the Next Wave: Strategies and Recommendations in E-Commerce

To fully use generative AI and other new technologies, e-commerce businesses must be strategic in their approach. With that in mind, the following are some steps to consider in preparation for technology's next wave. Therefore, businesses should invest in AI and data analytics to use the insights derived from such technologies. By collecting and analyzing customers' data, companies can facilitate or make available personalized experiences for customers and optimize their operations. More specifically, AI-driven customer insights have efficiently guided businesses in understanding clients' preferences and behaviors, guiding effective marketing strategies and product offerings (Green et al., 2022). Cybersecurity is becoming more critical as more data is collected and processed by e-commerce businesses. Robust security measures must be implemented to shield the consumers' data and ensure compliance with regulations such as GDPR. Blockchain technology will

also foster security because it is a secure and transparent way to conduct transactions (Rothenberg & Argawal, 2020). Businesses should, therefore, embrace cultures of innovation and collaboration. This is achievable through partnerships with technology providers, investments in research and development, and employee investment in new ideas. Staying ahead of the edge of these technological advances enables businesses to create innovative solutions that solve the needs of their customers (Williams, 2022).

Customer experience must be the center of all e-commerce strategies. Businesses must leverage generative AI, VR, and AR technologies to ensure engaging and personalized shopping experiences. For example, AI-driven virtual assistants shall always be available to assist customers instantly and provide customized recommendations. Similarly, VR and AR technologies can indulge customers in highly compelling shopping experiences (Kili, Inc., 2023; Voiceflow, Inc., 2023).

Sustainability is something the customers are looking for. Business processes, hence, need to understand, adapt, and embed sustainability to a large extent with the proper use of technologies such as AI and IoT. For example, AI facilitates supply chain management to minimize or decrease the production of extra products/wastes. At the same time, IoT's task is to monitor energy consumption patterns and identify areas through which improvements can be introduced. As technologies change rapidly, employees must be updated with the latest skills and knowledge. Business investments are needed in training and upskilling programs for workers to work effectively with new technologies. Training employees about AI, data analytics, cybersecurity, and other emerging technologies will help them better understand them (Lee et al., 2021). The business must monitor and access new updates of technologies uninterruptedly for it to keep competing favorably. This may mean keeping up with the latest trends, attending related industrial conferences, or interacting with some thought leaders to comment on new ideas. An upfront organization can quickly identify ways to incorporate new technologies into its processes (Williams, 2022).

5. Conclusion

Generative Artificial Intelligence is Changing the Game for E-commerce in these modern times. Generative AI is leaving its mark on e-commerce by changing how customer experience, product visualization, marketing, and content creation happen within this field of business. It completely fulfills the dynamic needs that customers seek in personalized, interactive, and instant interactions or experiences with their brands of choice. The ability to provide real-time, customized responses through generative AI has taken customer service to the next level. Wendy's Fresh AI is a perfect example of how AI can simplify processes and enhance order accuracy, lifting customer satisfaction and underpin operations. Virtual assistants such as Kili and Voiceflow prove how AI-driven chatbots facilitate the shopping process by guiding customers around products and readily offering support, thus resulting in higher conversions and increased satisfaction.

Developments like Solidgrids and Lumalabs.ai have modernized product visualization. These advancements enable e-commerce sites to seamlessly create quality, varietal product images, and 3D visuals without requiring expensive photoshoots. This allows customers to see much more realistic representations of products, thus yielding more conversions and a better shopping experience. Generative AI has also contributed significantly to marketing. Adcreative.ai and Maverick are highly effective tools enabling businesses to create personalized ad content that is conversion-oriented as well, thereby enabling the company to engage its audience while increasing engagement and conversions in turn. Customized video messaging also allows the brand to connect with its audience more profoundly, leaving room for brand loyalty and rising sales.

Despite the development, many challenges are evident in integrating Generative AI in shopping. Privacy is the most highlighted one, as personalization with AI requires the collection of loads of data. It is vital to ensure data privacy and security from the involved customer and comply with standard regulations like GDPR to avoid legal issues and retain the customer's trust in the brand. Secondly, AI systems sometimes mirror the same bias used in their training data. These biases must be overcome so AI-based shopping experiences are fair and inclusive. A balanced approach, wherein AI's capability is balanced with human interception, provides an optimum outcome in customer service and operational efficiency. This possibility of Generative AI for e-commerce is vast and very encouraging for the future. Also, enhanced personalization will further evolve, providing very customized shopping experiences to customers. Due to AI-powered virtual try-ons, consumers can see fashion

and beauty items on themselves before purchasing, thus making online shopping less of a guessing game. To that end, AI analysis of market trend information and customer data will inform dynamic pricing models to optimize revenue and customer satisfaction. Emerging technologies like blockchain, IoT, and quantum computing will further transform them. Blockchain provides secure and highly transparent transactions, enhancing security and lowering fraud. IoT interconnects products, customers, and retailers for effective shopping, including real-time inventory tracking and personalized recommendations. Quantum computing solves complex optimization problems and delivers logistical improvements in supply chain management and customized recommendations.

E-commerce companies are slowly adapting to use the potential of Generative AI and other new technologies. They must invest in AI and data analytics, develop tighter cybersecurity, and prioritize innovation and collaboration. However, they must stay laser-focused on customer experience, become more sustainable, train and upskill their people, and constantly scan the horizon for what is coming next. In other words, Generative AI will cause tremendous transformation in how e-commerce will be conducted, at least in terms of business operations and how clients will be handled. Once harnessed, AI's power requires its challenges to be surmounted so businesses can concoct new mechanisms that invigorate and satisfy customer needs and create a delightful experience for customers to continue doing better business with the organization. The future of Generative AI associated with e-commerce is full of promise. Companies should respond to these changes early to keep phase businesses relevant to these changing times in a dynamic and highly competitive space.

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